

The EVEREST Project: Toward Experimental Validation of Advanced Multi-Physics Tools for Fluence Source Term Calculation

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ABSTRACT

In the context of an aging nuclear power plant fleet and delays in new builds, a safe long-term operation of the current fleet is of paramount importance. One key parameter for the continuing operation of those plants is the pressure vessel fluence which must remain under a certain threshold to ensure a safe operation. The fluence is largely determined by the source term i.e. the neutron flux coming from the reactor core. In recent years, many advanced multi-physics simulation tools have been developed for a more accurate description of the core flux distribution and their application could help reduce conservatism in source term assessment while preserving safety margins. However, those methods are difficult to validate as the available measurements in Nuclear Power Plants do not match the high resolution of those methods. This is the motivation behind the EVEREST project, a four-year project funded by the Euratom research and training programme. The EVEREST project has two main objectives. First, to demonstrate the usefulness of advanced multi-physics simulation tools for the assessment of the source term needed for fluence calculation of both core internals and pressure vessel. This objective will be achieved by comparing the current conventional modelling approach with the advanced ones on a fluence case study on three European reactors. The second objective is to demonstrate the trustworthiness of said advanced multi-physics simulation tools by leveraging existing data as well as generating dedicated high resolution experimental data at three European research reactors.

Keywords: multi-physics, high resolution, vessel fluence, experimental validation

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of an aging nuclear power plant fleet and delays in new builds, Long Term Operation (LTO) of the current fleet is a focus of nuclear safety research. One key parameter for the continuing operation of those plants is the pressure vessel fluence which must remain under a certain threshold to ensure a safe operation. The fluence is largely determined by the source term i.e. the neutron flux coming from the reactor core. In recent years, many advanced multi-physics simulation tools have been developed for a more accurate description of the core flux distribution and their application could help reduce conservatism in source term assessment while preserving safety margins. However, those methods are difficult to validate as the available measurements in NPPs do not match the high resolution of those methods. This is the motivation behind the EVEREST project (*Experiments for Validation and Enhancement of the REactor preSsure vessel fluence assessment*), a four-year project funded by the Euratom research and training programme.

The EVEREST project has two main objectives. The first objective is to demonstrate the usefulness of advanced multi-physics simulation tools for the assessment of the source term needed for fluence calculation of both core internals and pressure vessel. This objective will be achieved by comparing the current modelling approach with the advanced ones on a fluence case study on three European reactors presented in the next section. The second objective is to demonstrate the trustworthiness of said advanced multi-physics simulation tools by leveraging existing data as well as generating dedicated

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high resolution experimental data at three European research reactors. A description of the reactors and the associated experiments is provided in Section 3.

The EVEREST consortium includes 15 institutions from a wide range of backgrounds, 4 of which are “associated partners” from outside the EU. Universities are represented by the Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL-Switzerland), the Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem (BME-Hungary), the North Carolina State University (NCSU-USA) and Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM-Spain). The consortium also features several research centers, including Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI-Switzerland), Energiatudományi Kutatóközpont (EK-Hungary), Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI-Slovenia). TSOs are represented by the Nuclear Safety and Radiation Protection Authority (ASNR-France), Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT (Finland) and the Gesellschaft für Anlagen- und Reaktorsicherheit (GRS-Germany), which acts as project coordinator with the support of LGE (France). Finally, the nuclear private sector is represented by companies such as PreussenElektra GmbH (Germany), Tractebel Engineering S.A. (Belgium), Axpo Power AG (Switzerland), and MVM Paks Nuclear Power Plant Ltd. (Hungary).

2. FLUENCE CASE STUDY ON THREE EXISTING PWRs

The first work package (WP1) of the project is dedicated to the industrial implications of using advanced multi-physics schemes for the determination of neutron fluence in the core internals and Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) of Nuclear Power Plants (NPP). The case study will be performed for 3 existing European pressurized water reactors, for which data have been made available by participating operators to selected participants:

- The Beznau Nuclear Power Plant (Switzerland), a 2-loop PWR with 121 rectangular fuel elements
- The Grohnde Nuclear Power Plant (Germany), a Vor-Konvoi PWR with 193 rectangular fuel elements
- The Paks Nuclear Power Plant (Hungaria), a VVER440 PWR with 349 hexagonal fuel elements

The computational approach to determine the RPV fluence relies on two consecutive steps: First, the determination of the neutron source in the periphery of the core through multi-physics simulations and in the second step, a fixed-source transport calculation using either a deterministic or a Monte Carlo transport code (the latter combined with variance reduction techniques).

The conventional modelling of the source term also relies on a two-step approach. First, sets of burnup and TH-dependent homogenized cross-sections are generated using a transport method in an infinite lattice. Those cross-section sets are then used in the second step by diffusion codes coupled with a thermal-hydraulics (TH) solver at the assembly level. Pin-power reconstruction methods are often used to determine the quantities of interest and their evolution during the cycles at the pin level. Before performing a comparison with the advanced schemes, a code-to-code comparison amongst the conventional models will be carried out to assess the spread of the results, and, when possible, code-to-plant data comparison will also be performed. The comparison will be made for parameters relevant for safety and/or operation such as, the boron let-down curve, power maps, maximum linear heat rate. The list of codes applied for conventional modelling is provided in the second column of Table I.

For the advanced multi-physics models, deterministic and probabilistic neutron transport solvers, as well as pin-level diffusion or SP_n, will be coupled to TH subchannel based approaches for the heat transfer and fluid flow. The use of CFD is not foreseen, as it is still too computationally expensive for full NPP core models. Both types of transport solvers are in principle capable of providing sub-pin level information, e.g., give access to the radial and azimuthal variations of the power produced within a fuel rod. Such information is not available from the lower-order approaches. Before performing a comparison with the conventional schemes, a code-to-code comparison amongst the advanced models will be carried out to assess the spread of the results, due to the nature of the neutron transport solution (deterministic vs stochastic) or the type of subchannel codes involved. The list of codes applied for advanced modelling is provided in the third column of Table II.

Figure 1. Top left: 1/4 core representation of a 121 rectangular fuel assembly PWR core – Top right: 1/4 core representation of a 193 rectangular fuel assembly PWR core – Bottom: 1/6 core representation of a 349 hexagonal fuel assembly VVER440 core

Table I. Partners and codes aiming conventional and advanced source term determination

Institute	Conventional codes	Advanced codes
EPFL	SCALE [1]/PARCS [2]	MPACT [3] coupled to CTF [4]
GRS	KMACS [5]	FENNECS [6] at pin resolution coupled to CTF
HUN-REN EK	KARATE [7] code system	KARATE code system with advanced methods
ASNR	CASMO [8]/SIMULATE [9]	-
NCSU	-	Serpent [10] coupled to CTF
PSI	CASMO/SIMULATE	nTRACER [11] coupled to CTF
TRACTEBEL	WIMS/PANTHER [12]	PANTHERS`s embedded route (Pin-by-pin 2d diffusion)
UPM	SCALE/COBAYA [13]	COBAYA at pin resolution coupled to CTF
VTT	Serpent/Ants-Kharon [14]	Serpent/SUBCHANFLOW [15]

In order to increase the consistency between conventional and advanced approaches, the same transport code will be used for both approaches (when possible). For example, at VTT, a specific comparison will involve a conventional model using the ANTS nodal solver and the nodal parameters generated with Serpent; and an advanced model relying on Serpent coupled to SUBCHANFLOW. The use of the Serpent in both schemes will allow for consistency in terms of nuclear data. Consistency of the thermal hydraulic feedback will be achieved by using assembly level information produced by the conventional scheme (Kharon solver) in the advanced approach. Then conventional and advanced schemes will be compared in terms of the quantities of interest.

The Monte Carlo transport models for fluence calculation will be applied (at least) twice: Once with the source term from the conventional approach and once with the source term from the advanced multi-physics model. The objective is to quantify the impact of advanced modelling on the fluence which is the parameter most important for LTO. The list of codes applied for advanced modelling is provided in Table II.

Table II. Partners and codes aiming fluence calculations

Institute	Codes
AXPO	Serpent
HUN-REN EK	MCNP/ADVANTG [15]
IRSN	MCNP/ADVANTG
PSI	MCNP/ADVANTG
TRACTEBEL	MCBEND
UPM	MAVRIC (SCALE package)
VTT	Serpent

Finally, these simulations will be complemented by uncertainty analysis using the existing frameworks at GRS and PSI. The uncertainties associated with the nuclear data as well as various thermal-hydraulics (e.g. inlet mass flow and temperature), technological parameters (e.g. fuel compositions, geometry, etc...) and boundary conditions (irradiation conditions) will be considered. The uncertainty analyses will be limited to the conventional computational schemes since they require a large number of simulations. The output resulting from the random input samples will be used for the representativity analysis envisioned in the experimental design.

3. VALIDATION OF HIGH-RESOLUTION MULTI-PHYSICS MODELS USING RESEARCH REACTORS

Two work packages (WP2 and WP3) are dedicated to the validation of high-resolution multi-physics models. For this purpose, advanced multi-physics models of the research reactors involved in the project will be developed. The advanced models will be as close as possible (codes, level of discretization, etc...) to the one used for the nuclear power plant modelling of work package 1. The three research reactors are:

- The Training Reactor of BME: a light-water moderated and cooled reactor of 100 kW nominal thermal power.
- The TRIGA Mark II research reactor of JSI: a pool type reactor of 250 kW nominal power. It is well characterized in terms of neutron and gamma fields; it is also capable of pulse mode operation.
- The Budapest Research Reactor (EK): a light water-cooled, light water-moderated reactor of 10 MW nominal thermal power.

Within WP2, for each of the three modelled reactors, a set of experimental data relevant for the assessment of feedback effects in multi-physics modelling will be produced, either from new experiments or from existing campaigns. Focus is given to the determination of local quantities (neutron flux, temperature) in research reactors with the best possible resolution using instrumentation available on site or within the consortium; as well as existing experimental setup. For each of the three research reactors, the following experiments are planned: a pulse experiment at the TRIGA reactor from

JSI, a series of quasi-stationary states and slow transients (power ramps) at the Training Reactor of BME and steady state irradiations for different (high) power levels at the EK reactor.

Figure 2. Top left: View of the BME Training reactor – Top right: View of the EK Budapest research reactor – Bottom: View of the TRIGA reactor at JSI

Those experiments will be simulated by the conventional and advanced models listed in Table III. Code-to-code comparison and especially code-to-experiments comparison will be carried out. Measurements will be provided for neutron flux and water temperature. Fuel temperatures will be simulated but no direct measurements are possible.

Table III. Partners and codes aiming the research reactors

Reactor	Conventional model		Advanced models			
			Model 1		Model 2	
	Code	Institute	Code	Institute	Code	Institute
JSI	TRIGLAV [17]	JSI	Serpent / OpenFOAM	VTT	FENNECS/CTF	GRS
BME	TRACE/PARCS	BME	MPACT/CTF	EPFL	FENNECS/CTF	GRS
EK	KIKO3D[18]/ BREKI	EK	GenFOAM [19]	EPFL	nTRACER/CTF	PSI

At this point the experimental data will still be at a resolution significantly lower than the one provided by the advanced multi-physics tools. This is why the main objective of WP3 is to perform new multi-physics experiments of benchmark quality for the validation of advanced multi-physics models, specifically targeting a better spatial resolution.

In order to do so, dedicated new experiments will be designed. New detector types with an improved spatial resolution will be developed. For this purpose, the zero-power facility CROCUS of EPFL will be involved for the testing of the novel fiber-based instrumentation (neutron flux and temperature measurement). The experiments will be performed at the Training reactor of BME and the TRIGA Mark II reactor of JSI.

Finally, these simulations will be complemented by uncertainty analysis using the existing frameworks at GRS and EPFL. The uncertain parameters will be selected to match the ones analysed in WP1. The output of the uncertainty analysis (mainly the sensitivity indices of the computational models) will be compared with the results of WP1. From this comparison, a set of “representativity indices” will be produced. A high representativity index indicates that the computational model closely mirrors the experimental setup.

4. EDUCATION AND DISSEMINATION

Education of the dissemination of the project results are main objectives of the EVEREST project and the focus of a work package (WP4). EVEREST will fully embrace the open access policy of Horizon Europe, favouring Gold Open Access whenever possible.

One main outcome of this WP is the organization of a Summer School for Master and PhD students and professionals on multi-physics methods and a training course for nuclear regulators on the advantages of high-fidelity nuclear reactor modelling. The goal of the Summer School is to provide university students, researchers and/or physicists/engineers working with technical support organizations an opportunity to learn how to use advanced multi-physics codes for reactor modelling. The importance of validation experiments for advanced multi-physics methods will be an important aspect of the Summer School.

The other, equally important outcome of this work package is to organize a training course for NPP operators and regulators to enhance their awareness on the advantages of the application of advanced multi-physics methods for power plant reactor modelling.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that part of the research conducted within the project is being carried out by researchers pursuing their Doctoral Thesis. Specific mobility grants have been established within WP4 to support PhD and Master students, facilitating their access to research reactors and promoting scientific exchange between the EVEREST consortium partners. Several doctoral dissertations have already been initiated. By supporting PhD dissertations, the project demonstrates its commitment to the education and training of a highly qualified workforce that benefits the project itself, the PhD students, their home institutions, and the reactor physics community while contributing to meeting future industry and research needs.

5. CONCLUSIONS

By quantifying the impact of high-resolution multi-physics schemes on the vessel fluence calculation, which is an important parameter in the scope of LTO, the EVEREST project aims at showing the usefulness of such advanced methods compared with the current approach. By using detailed (old and new) measurements in various research reactors, the EVEREST project aims at showing the trustworthiness of those advanced methods. This two-thronged approach will be supplemented by uncertainty analyses which will be used to assess the representativity of the conditions found in research reactors compared to the conditions in NPP cores. The modelling as well as the experimental work have started for both NPP and research reactors and first results can be found in several papers presented in at this year’s PHYSOR conference.

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